

TALABALARDA TANQIDIY FIKRLASHNI RIVOJLANTIRISH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7954740>

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada tanqidiy fikrlashni asosi, kelib chiqishi va uning talabalarning ilmiy va ijodiy faoliyatida tugan o'rni rivojlanish omillari asoslar va fikr mulohazalar bilan keltirib o'tildi.

Tayanch so'zlar: Tanqidiy fikrlash bu, hokimiyat (obro'), Barri K.Beyer (1995), talabalar o'z g'oyalari, talabalarning erkin, kreativ.

РАЗВИТИЕ КРИТИЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ У УЧАЩИХСЯ

Аннотация. В данной статье были представлены основания и происхождение критического мышления и его роль в научной и творческой деятельности студентов, факторы развития, причины и мнения.

Основные слова: Критическое мышление – это авторитет (авторитет), Барри К. Бейер (1995), студенты владеют идеями, студенты свободны, креативны.

DEVELOPMENT OF CRITICAL THINKING IN STUDENTS

Abstract. In this article, the basis and origin of critical thinking and its role in the scientific and creative activities of students, development factors were presented with reasons and opinions.

Keywords: Critical thinking is authority (authority), Barry K. Beyer (1995), students own ideas, students are free, creative.

Kirish Tanqidiy fikrlash bilan bog'liq eng qadimgi yozuvlar Platon tomonidan yozilgan Suqrot ta'limotini taqdim etgan dialoglardir. Ular Platonning birinchi dialoglari bo'lib, Suqrot bir yoki bir nechta suhbatdoshlari bilan axloqiy masalalar, masalan, Suqrotning qamoqdan qochishi to'g'ri bo'ladimi, degan mavzuda gaplashadi. Faylasuf bu masalani o'ylab, mulohaza yuritadi va shunday xulosaga keladi: qochish uning ustida tutgan barcha narsalarni (qadriyatlarini) buzadi, masalan, Afina qonunlari va Suqrot tinglayman, degan ichki rahbar ovoz. Suqrot tanqidiy haqiqatni aniqlab berdiki, inson bilim va aqlga „hokimiyat“ (obro') asosida bog'liq bo'lmaydi. U hokimiyat va yuqori lavozim egalari juda sarosimali va mantiqsiz bo'lishi mumkinligini isbotladi. Tanqidiy fikrlash — fikrlashning alohida turi bo'lib, faktlarni tahlil qilish orqali xulosalar hosil qiladi. Ushbu konsepsiya murakkab va turli xil ta'riflarga ega, jumladan, ratsionallik, skeptitsizm, xolis tahlil va faktlarni tekshirish. Tanqidiy fikrlash bu — o'z-o'zini boshqaradigan, o'zini o'zi tarbiyalaydigan, o'zini o'zi nazorat qiladigan va o'zini o'zi to'g'iraydigan fikrlash shaklidir. Uning zaruriy sharti ongni takomillashtirishning qat'iy me'yorlariga rozi bo'lish va ularni hushyorlik bilan qo'llashdir.

Adabiyotlar tahlili. Tanqidiy fikrlash Richard V.Pol tomonidan ikki to'liqinli harakat sifatida tasvirlangan (1994). Tanqidiy fikrlashning „birinchi to'liqini“ ko'pincha „tanqidiy tahlil“, tanqidni o'z ichiga olgan sof, oqilona fikrlash deb ataladi. Uning tafsilotlari unga murojaat

qilganlar orasida farq qiladi. Barri K.Beyer (1995) fikriga ko'ra, tanqidiy fikrlash aniq, asosli hukm chiqarishni anglatadi. Tanqidiy fikrlash jarayonida g'oyalar isbotlanishi, to'liq ko'rib chiqilishi va baholanishi kerak. Tanqidiy fikrlash qobiliyatlari bo'yicha AQSh Milliy kengashi tanqidiy fikrlashni quyidagicha ta'riflaydi: "kuzatish, tajriba, mulohaza yuritish, mulohazalar yoki muloqot orqali to'plangan yoki hosil qilingan ma'lumotlarni e'tiqod va harakatni (kontseptuallashtirish) boshqaradigan tushunchalarga faol va mohirona aylantirish, qo'llash, tahlil qilish, sintez qilish yoki baholashning intellektual, ilg'or jarayoni sifatida aniqlanadi. Ko'pincha e'tiqodlarimizda emotsional yoki boshqa ruhiy investitsiyalarga ega bo'lganimiz sababli, odamlarning mantig'i yoki dalillari zaifmi-yo'qligiga qaramay, odamlar oldinga qadam qo'yish va bu e'tiqodlarni himoya qilishga urinish odatiy emas. Darhaqiqat, ba'zida odamlar bu haqda ko'p narsa bilmasalar ham, ular fikrlarini himoya qiladi - ular o'ylaydi, lekin ular yo'q. Biroq, tanqidiy fikrlashni o'rganishga harakat qiladigan kishi, bilish kerak bo'lgan hamma narsani allaqachon bilgan deb o'ylashdan qochishga harakat qiladi. Bunday kishi, norozi bo'lgan kishilar ularga tegishli narsalarni o'rgatishi va muhim, tegishli dalillarni bilmagan holda pozitsiyani tortib olishdan bosh tortishlariga yo'l qo'yishga tayyor. Tanqidiy fikrlashda erkinlik bo'lishi uchun talabalar ma'qul va noma'qul narsalarni aytish, ular qaqida fikrlash, ijod qilish uchun ruxsat olishlari lozim. Talabalar yo'l qo'yiladigan xolatlarni anglab olishgach, tanqidiy taqlil qilishga faol kirishadilar. Tanqidiy taqlilga izn olish onglilik tamoyiliga asoslanadi. Bunda taqlil va xaddan oshish orasidagi farq aniqlab berilishi lozim. Tanqidiy fikrlashga izn fikrlash uchun chinakam maqsad bo'lgan va do'stona hamda samarali sharoitda beriladi. Tanqidiy fikrlashning omillaridan biri talabalarning fikrlash jarayonini qadrlashdir. Talabalar o'z fikrlash jarayonini qadrlashni namoyish qilishga qarakat qiladilar, unga va uning oqibatlariga nisbatan jiddiy munosabatda bo'la boshlaydilar. Fikrlash jarayonini tashkil etish davomida talaba ularning fikrlari, o'z tanqidiy taqlili natijalari qimmatli ekanligini ularning ongiga singdirish zarur. O'qituvchi talabalardan muayyan materialni shunchaki qayta ishlashni talab qilganda tayyor qoliplardan, andozalardan holi bo'lishi lozim. Bu esa talabalarda o'zgaralar g'oyalarini mexanik tarzda qayta ishlab chiqish eng muhim va qimmatli ekanligiga ishonch qosil qilishga olib keladi.

Tahlillar va natijalar. Talabalarni tavakkaldan holi bo'lgan, ya'ni g'oyalar qadrlangan, talabalarning fikrlash faoliyatida faol ishtirokini yuqori motivatsiyalash imkoni bo'lgan muhitda o'ylash lozimligi haqida ularda ishonch hosil qilish zarur. Muayyan mavzu yoki vaziyatga qiziqmaydigan odam hech qachon bu haqda tanqidiy fikrlash mashqlarini bajara olmaydi. Buning sababi shundaki, barcha ma'lumotlarni to'plash va xolisona tahlil qilish uchun siz nima bo'layotganini bilishni juda xohlashingiz kerak. Shu sababli tanqidiy xulosalarni shakllantirishga qodir odamlar tug'ma tabiatan qiziquvchan yoki ba'zi hollarda uni ishlab chiqarishni o'rganganlar. Shaxs mustaqil fikrlay olishi kerak Olingan barcha ma'lumotlarni qabul qilib, inson hech qachon tanqidiy fikrlash qobiliyatini rivojlantira olmaydi. Aksincha, unga erishmoqchi bo'lgan kishi uchun, u haqiqatni haqiqatdan boshqasini ajratish uchun, qabul qilgan barcha fikr va faktlarni tahlil qila olishi kerak. Xuddi shu sababga ko'ra tanqidiy fikrlashni ishlatishga qodir bo'lgan odam bilan osonlikcha manipulyatsiya qilinmaydi: har doim eshitganlari haqida mulohaza yuritish orqali u haqiqatni bo'lmagan narsadan ajrata oladi. Ijodiy fikrlashni talab qiladi U har bir eshitgan narsasiga ishonishi mumkin emasligi sababli, tanqidiy fikrlaydigan kishi turli muammolarning yangi echimlarini topishi kerak; shu tariqa siz o'zingizning javoblaringizni yaratishingiz mumkin, hatto ularni hali hech kim topmagan bo'lsa ham. Tanqidiy fikrlash poyezdining rivojlanishi jarayonida

6-sezgi yordamga kelishi mumkin. Narsalar, hodisalar, harakatlar haqida taxminlar ongsiz darajada mavjud. Sezgi mantiqqa bo'ysunmaydi, lekin qaror qabul qilish uchun qo'shimcha sifatida qimmatlidir. Tanqidiy fikrlash tabiiy jarayon, oddiy fikrlash poyezdidir, deb ishoniladi. Biroq, ichida hayotiy vaziyatlar odamlar undan chetga chiqadilar. Talalarda ham tafakkurni tarbiyalash va rivojlantirish hayot sifatini yaxshilash, qabul qilish demakdir to'g'ri qarorlar va hayotda muvaffaqiyatga erishing. Fikrlash jarayoni nazariy ilm va amaliyot vaqtida dunyoga to'g'ri qarashni shakllantiradi va mantiqni rivojlantiradi.

Fikrlashning rivojlanishi ko'p foyda keltiradi. Bularga quyidagilar kiradi:

- to'g'ri xulosalar chiqarish qobiliyati;
- kerakli ma'lumotlarni to'plash qobiliyati;
- asoslash va mulohaza yuritish qobiliyati;
- muammoni aniq tushunish qobiliyati;
- g'oyalardan foydalanish qobiliyati;
- odamlar bilan muloqot qilish;
- muqobil fikrlashdan foydalanish qobiliyati.

Tanqidiy fikrlashni rivojlantirgandan so'ng, inson o'z xulosalarini to'g'rilab, bir yo'nalishda o'ylay boshlaydi. Bunday fikrlash standartlardan farq qiladi va murakkab muammolarni hal qilish imkonini beradi.

Xulosalar. Demak to'g'ri va haqiqat bo'lgan g'oyalar mavjud, lekin oxirgisiga tegishli bo'lgan g'oyaga ega bo'lishni istasak-da, biz so'nggi guruhning juda qadimdan, juda kichik ekanligini tushunishimiz kerak. Aksincha, aksariyat hollarda, ko'p narsalar haqida, xususan, ko'p munozaralarning asosiy mavzusi bo'lgan narsalar haqida mutlaqo aniq ma'lumot yo'q. Biror kishi shubha-gumonlik va tanqidiy fikrlashni mashq qilganda, ular o'zlarini xulosa chiqarishga shubha bilan qarashlari mumkinligini eslashadi, bu ularning haqiqatan ham to'g'ri ekanligini ko'rsatib qo'yganini yoki ko'rsatishi mumkin emasligini anglatadi. Ba'zi haqiqatlar qat'iy ishonchni talab qiladi, ammo mumkin bo'lgan haqiqatlar faqat dalillarga asoslangan ishonchni talab etadi, ya'ni dalil va sababga ko'ra ularga xuddi shu kuchga ishonishimiz kerak. Mazkur fikrlar va muloxazalar talabalarning erkin, kreativ va keng ma'noda dunyoda o'larining ideal o'rinlarini topishi uchun bir muncha asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

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